

CUSP Workshop Series Human Risk Assessment

Workshop 3/3 Data Needs

EU POLYRISK: Perspective & Contributions

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The general risk assessment paradigm

Substance Identity

Chemical Composition (Impurities?)

In some cases incl. key characteristics (e.g. for nanomaterials: size, morphology, surface area, surface treatment)

Exposure Assessment

Who? Route? How often? How long? Dose? etc.

Hazard Identification

What health problems/ adverse effects? Target organ(s)?

Dose Response Assessment

Threshold? How does hazard change with dose?

Risk characterization

Is there a risk? For whom? How big is the risk?

Risk assessment for Micro- and Nanoplastics (MNPs)

MNPs Characterization

- **Chemical Characterization**
 - Polymer Type (PE, PP, PVC ...)
 - Residual monomers, oligomers
 - Additives
 - Contaminants
- **Key Phys. Chem. Parameters**
 - **Size** (Size distribution?)
 - **Morphology**

POLYRISK Focus

- PP, PE, PET (pristine & aged)
- Basic physicochem. properties
- Characterization of aerosols

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Hazard (Identification & Characterization)

- **Morphology- triggered Hazards**
 - Fibre MoA
 - general particle effects
- **Substance- specific Hazards**
 - leaching of monomers
 - leaching of additives
 - release of contaminants

POLYRISK Focus

- Lung
 - Uptake/ Transport across barrier
 - Local Effects
- Immune-related effects

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Exposure

- **Exposure Route**
- **External Dose**
- **Internal Dose**

POLYRISK Focus

- Inhalation
- Real World Scenarios

Useful Concepts: IATAs

Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment

OECD IATA Activities

<https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/iata/>

- flexible approaches for chemical safety assessment
- integrate data from multiple methods/ sources, may include New Approach Methods (NAMs) such as high throughput screening or computational methods
- provide a **logical combinations of tests and assessments** (outcome of one step determines the next); **overall assessment conducted with a minimum of new experiments**
- can be based on **AOP concepts**

DRAFT POLYRISK Risk Assessment Framework for MNPs

Exposure Scenario

Is inhalation exposure expected?

Yes

Can MNP be inhaled?

Yes

Can MNP reach distal lung?

Yes

Basic Phys- Chem Characterization

Size
(Aerodynamic Diameter)

Morphology

Does MNP have a fibre morphology?

Yes

No

Distinction

Potentially Critical
Polymeric Fibres

Non Critical
Polymeric Fibres

Grouping

Distinction

Polymeric Particles of
Low Concern

Polymeric Particles
with Concern

Grouping

Case by Case
Assessment

EXPOSURE: POLYRISK Real World Scenarios

Oral

Consumer

MNP in bottled drinking water

Inhalation

Worker

Textile fibre workplace exposure

General Population

Urban and rural outdoor air ambient MNP

Air exposure at tire rubber refurbishing workplaces

Indoor Soccer Players (rubber granulate-MNP)

Future Plan: Use Exposure Models (in particular MPPD- model, US EPA)

Sampling & Characterization: POLYRISK Method Development

Sampling

- 1) Protocol for analysis of air samples (incl. diff. filtration systems)
- 2) Protocol(s) for liquid sample filtration (different types of filters)
- 3) Protocols for blood analysis

Characterization of MNP Aerosols

Filtration system for liquid samples developed by partner CSP

Example:
Correlative microscopy
(Identification and Counting of MNP-Aerosols on Nucleopore filters)

POLYRISK Hazard Characterization

Example: Particle Uptake

van den Berg et al. 2022 (J. Immunotox, accepted)

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POLYRISK Hazard Characterization

Cytotoxicity

(macrophages, epithelial cells, neutrophils, myeloid cells)

Inflammation

Cell Activation

(macrophages, epithelial cells, neutrophils, myeloid cells)

Inflammatory mediators release

Recruitment of e.g. neutrophils

Reactivity & Cellular ox. stress

Acellular particle reactivity

(e.g. FRAS, DCFDA assay)

Cellular oxidative stress (in vitro)

(various assays, macrophages, epithelial cells, neutrophils, myeloid cells)

KEY EVENTS CENTRAL TO MANY INFLAMMATORY DISEASE OUTCOMES

Representing the Process of Inflammation as Key Events in Adverse Outcome Pathways

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Thank you for your attention.

